

Synthesis, spectral characterization and single crystal X-ray diffraction study of arylazoimidazolium tetraiodobismuthate(III) compounds[†]

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Abstract : Eight new organic-inorganic hybrid compounds of 1,3-dialkyl-2-(arylo)imidazolium, [RaaR'R'']⁺, and [Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ ion are synthesized. The structure has been established by spectral (FT-IR, UV-Vis, ¹H NMR) data and the structural confirmation has been done by single crystal X-ray diffraction study in case of [MeaaMe₂⁺]₄[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (where MeaaMe₂⁺ = 1,3-dimethyl-2-(*p*-tolylazo)imidazolium). The DFT computation has been used to explain the electronic structure and the electronic spectra of the compounds.

Keywords : Dialkyl-aryloimidazolium salt, spectra, X-ray structure, DFT computation.

Introduction

Organic-inorganic hybrid ionic compounds have attracted attention for their high mechanical and dimensional stability, high conductivity, large potential window supporting electrolyte for fuel cells etc.¹⁻⁶. Metal-halides of transition and nontransition metals have generated halometallates, building agent to bring organic cations together to develop sustainable hybrid materials⁷⁻⁹. Iodide (I⁻) has generated polymeric network with most of the metal ions and form myriad of bridged dimmers, cubanes, chains, strands, etc.⁷⁻¹². The N-heterocycle organic cations like dialkyl imidazolium iodides are interesting class of ionic liquids with low vapor pressure and are important media for organic and inorganic compound synthesis and in separation processes¹³⁻¹⁵. Aryloimidazoles have given us a chance to synthesize good number of metal complexes¹⁶⁻²⁰ and also ionic compounds upon protonation or double alkylation²¹⁻²⁵. Alkylation of arylazoimidazoles has synthesized 1,3-dialkyl-2-(arylo)imidazolium salts of different anions like PF₆⁻²¹, ReO₄⁻^{22,23}, Cl⁻, [ZnCl₄]²⁻, [PtCl₆]²⁻²⁴, [PbI₃]⁻²⁵. Other groups of workers are also contributing to enrich this field with the studies of structural diversity of

aryloimidazolium ions with different oxo and nonoxo anions^{26,27}. In this work we report arylazoimidazolium salts of iodobismuthate(III). The compounds are characterized by different spectroscopic studies and structural confirmation has been done in representative cases by single crystal X-ray diffraction measurements.

Experimental materials

1,3-Dialkyl-2-(arylo)imidazoles were prepared by the reported procedure²⁸. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade as received. Bismuth iodide was purchased from S. D. Fine Chemicals Co.

Physical measurements

Microanalytical data (C, H, N) were collected on Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. Spectroscopic data were obtained using the following instruments : UV-Vis spectra from Perkin-Elmer Lambda 25 spectrophotometer; IR spectra (KBr disk, 4000-450 cm⁻¹) from Perkin-Elmer RX-1 FTIR spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra from Bruker (AC) 300 MHz FTNMR spectrometer. Molar conductance was measured using Systronics-304 conductivity meter.

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Preparation of compounds

The 1-alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazoles (RaaiR') were synthesized from the corresponding 2-(arylo)imidazoles (RaaiH, 1-3) by reacting the latter with the respective alkyl halide in the presence of sodium hydride in dry THF¹⁶.

Preparation of 1,3-dimethyl-2-(*p*-tolylazo)imidazolium iodide [MeaaiMe₂]⁺I⁻ (4b)

To THF solution (10 cm³) of 1-methyl-2-(*p*-tolylazo)imidazole (0.2 g, 1.00 mmol), MeI was added at low temperature bath for 30 min and then reflux for 4 h. The solution was evaporated under reduced pressure and the dry mass was extracted in water and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated slowly in air and orange crystalline products were isolated. The product was then recrystallised from methanol-water (1 : 1, v/v). Orange-red needle shaped crystals were isolated (0.24 g, 68%).

All other compounds were prepared by identical procedure in the yield of 65–75%.

Synthesis of [MeaaiMe₂]⁺[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (8b)

To methanol solution (15 cm³) of [MeaaiMe₂]⁺I⁻ (1,3-dimethyl-2-(*p*-tolylazo)imidazolium iodide) (0.125 g, 0.36 mmol), BiI₃ (0.21 g, 0.36 mmol) was added at a time, stirred and then refluxed for 10 h. The solution was filtered through G4 gooch and was left in air to evaporate slowly. Block shaped red crystals deposited on the wall of beaker and were collected by filtration. These crystals were grinded and 2-methoxy-ethanol solution was prepared. Methanol (2 volume) was added into this solution. After a week bright orange-red colored block shaped crystals deposited at the base of the beaker were collected and dried over CaCl₂ in dessicator. The yield was 62%.

All other complexes were prepared by the same procedure. In all cases, crystalline products were obtained. The yield varied from 70–80%. The microanalytical data of the complexes are as follows : [HaaiMe₂]⁺[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (8a) *Anal.* Found : C, 14.42; H, 1.40; N, 6.11. *Calcd.* : C, 14.40; H, 1.43; N, 6.10. FT-IR (KBr disc, cm⁻¹), $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1435; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1592 cm⁻¹. UV-Vis spectral data in DMF (λ_{max} (nm) (10⁻³ ∈ (dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)) : 283 (8.1), 370 (12.72), 462 (1.53). [MeaaiMe₂]⁺[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (8b) *Anal.* Found : C, 15.49; H, 1.60; N, 6.00. *Calcd.* : C, 15.47; H, 1.62; N, 6.01. FT-IR (KBr disc, cm⁻¹), $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1441; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1597 cm⁻¹. UV-Vis spectral data in DMF (λ_{max} (nm) (10⁻³ ∈ (dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)) : 286 (8.5), 373 (12.4), 466 (1.36). [HaaiEt₂]⁺[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (9a)

Anal. Found : C, 16.53; H, 1.78; N, 5.94. *Calcd.* : C, 16.51; H, 1.80; N, 5.92. FT-IR (KBr disc, cm⁻¹), $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1431; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1595 cm⁻¹. UV-Vis spectral data in DMF (λ_{max} (nm) (10⁻³ ∈ (dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)) : 284 (8.8), 372 (12.60), 467 (1.20). [MeaaiEt₂]⁺[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (9b) *Anal.* Found : C, 17.50; H, 1.97; N, 5.81. *Calcd.* : C, 17.52; H, 2.00; N, 5.84. FT-IR (KBr disc, cm⁻¹), $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1433; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1599 cm⁻¹. UV-Vis spectral data in DMF (λ_{max} (nm) (10⁻³ ∈ (dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)) : 285 (8.4), 372 (12.59), 469 (1.33). [Haai(CH₂Ph)₂]⁺[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (10a) *Anal.* Found : C, 25.85; H, 2.01; N, 5.20. *Calcd.* : C, 25.82; H, 1.98; N, 5.23. FT-IR (KBr disc, cm⁻¹), $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1437; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1590 cm⁻¹. UV-Vis spectral data in DMF (λ_{max} (nm) (10⁻³ ∈ (dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)) : 288 (8.9), 373 (12.73), 462 (1.46). [Meaai(CH₂Ph)₂]⁺[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (10b) *Anal.* Found : C, 26.58; H, 2.12; N, 5.15. *Calcd.* : C, 26.60; H, 2.14; N, 5.17. FT-IR (KBr disc, cm⁻¹), $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1442; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1597 cm⁻¹. UV-Vis spectral data in DMF (λ_{max} (nm) (10⁻³ ∈ (dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)) : 281 (8.3), 371 (12.76), 464 (1.39). [HaaiMe(CH₂Ph)⁺]₄[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (11a) *Anal.* Found : C, 20.51; H, 1.74; N, 5.66. *Calcd.* : C, 20.54; H, 1.72; N, 5.64. FT-IR (KBr disc, cm⁻¹), $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1436; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1587 cm⁻¹. UV-Vis spectral data in DMF (λ_{max} (nm) (10⁻³ ∈ (dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)) : 289 (8.2), 374 (12.38), 466 (1.36). [MeaaiMe(CH₂Ph)⁺]₄[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (11b) *Anal.* Found : C, 21.47; H, 1.78; N, 5.58. *Calcd.* : C, 21.45; H, 1.80; N, 5.56. FT-IR (KBr disc, cm⁻¹), $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1440; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1598 cm⁻¹. UV-Vis spectral data in CH₃CN (λ_{max} (nm) (10⁻³ ∈ (dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)) : 282 (8.2), 377 (12.47), 469 (1.31).

X-Ray crystal structure analyses

Crystal suitable for X-ray diffraction study of [MeaaiMe₂]⁺[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (8b) (0.25 × 0.20 × 0.13 mm) were prepared by slow evaporation of a solution of methanol and 2-methoxy-ethanol mixture (2 : 1 v/v) at ambient condition. Diffraction data were collected with the Bruker SMART 1K CCD area-detector diffractometer using fine focused sealed tube graphite-monochromatized Mo K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). Unit cell parameters were determined from least-squares method in the range of $-16 \leq h \leq 16$, $-17 \leq k \leq 17$, $-17 \leq l \leq 17$ and angle varies $3.2 < 2\theta < 52.20^\circ$ for 8b. A summary of the crystallographic data and structure refinement parameters are given in Table 1. Data were corrected for Lorentz and polarization effects. Data reduction was carried out by using SAINT programme. The structure was solved by direct

Table 1. Summarized crystallographic data for [MeaaiMe₂⁺]₄[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (**8b**)

Empirical formula	(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₄) ₄ Bi ₄ I ₁₆
Formula weight	3727.44
Temperature (K)	293(2)
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> -1
Crystal size (mm) ³	0.25 × 0.20 × 0.13
<i>a</i> (Å)	13.5698(14)
<i>b</i> (Å)	14.0033(15)
<i>c</i> (Å)	14.0356(15)
α (°)	88.331(2)
β (°)	69.900(2)
γ (°)	61.782(2)
<i>V</i> (Å) ³	2178.1(4)
<i>Z</i>	1
λ (Å)	0.71073
μ (Mo-Kα) (mm ⁻¹)	13.8
<i>D</i> _{calcd.} (mg m ⁻³)	2.842
<i>hkl</i> range	-16 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 16, -17 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 17, -17 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 17
θ range (°)	1.6–26.1
Refine parameters	379
Total reflection	8527
Unique data [<i>I</i> > 2σ (<i>I</i>)]	6654
<i>R</i> ₁ ^a [<i>I</i> > 2σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.0342
<i>wR</i> ₂ ^b	0.0821
Goodness of fit	1.025
Δ _{max} (e Å ⁻³)	1.27
Δ _{min} (e Å ⁻³)	-1.21
^a <i>R</i> = Σ <i>F</i> _o - <i>F</i> _c /Σ <i>F</i> _o , ^b <i>wR</i> = [Σ <i>w</i> (<i>F</i> _o ² - <i>F</i> _c ²)/Σ <i>w</i> <i>F</i> _o ⁴] ^{1/2} and <i>w</i> = 1/[σ ² (<i>F</i> ²) + (0.0348 <i>P</i>) ²] for 8b where <i>P</i> = (<i>F</i> _o ² + 2 <i>F</i> _c ²)/3.	

method using SHELXS-97²⁹ and successive difference Fourier syntheses. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Full matrix least squares refinements on *F*_o² were carried out using SHELXL-97³⁰ with anisotropic displacement parameters for all non-hydrogen atoms. Hydrogen atoms were constrained to ride on the respective carbon or nitrogen atoms with anisotropic displacement parameters equal to 1.2 times the equivalent isotropic displacement of their parent atom in all cases. All calculations were carried out using SHELXS97²⁹, PLATON99³¹, ORTEP-3³² programs.

Computation details

All the calculations were carried out with the density functional theory (DFT) method as implemented in

GAUSSIAN 03 (G03) program package³³ and the calculations have been performed using the B3LYP exchange correlation functional³⁴. The geometry of the compound **8b** were fully optimized in gas phase using 6-31G* basis set for all elements except bismuth and iodine. The Los Alamos effective core potential plus double zeta (LanL2DZ)³⁵ basis set was employed along with the corresponding pseudo potential of bismuth and iodine without any symmetry constrain. The vibrational frequency calculation was also performed for both compounds to ensure that the optimized geometries represent the local minima and there are only positive eigen values. The calculated and experimental metric parameters agree well to support proper selection of methods and functions used. To assign the low lying electronic transitions in the experimental spectra, TDDFT³⁶ calculations of the complexes were done in acetonitrile using conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM)^{37–39} with larger basis set 6-31g+(d) for H, C, N and LanL2DZ for bismuth and iodine.

Results and discussion

Upon alkylation of 2-(arylo)imidazole (RaaiH, R = H, *p*-Me) or 1-alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazole (RaaiR' where, R' = Me (1), Et (2) and CH₂Ph (3)) with alkylhalide (R'I) has synthesized 1,3-dialkyl-2-(arylo)imidazolium iodides, [RaaiR'₂]⁺I⁻ (R = H (a), Me (b); R' = Me (4), Et (5), CH₂Ph (6)) or unsymmetrical dialkyl salt. The purification of the products has been done by crystallization from methanol-water. Unsymmetrical imidazolium iodide, [Raai(Me)CH₂Ph]⁺I⁻ (7) are synthesized by benzylation of 1-methyl-2-(arylo)imidazoles (RaaiMe) with benzylchloride (PhCH₂Cl). Ionic compounds of the composition, [RaaiR'₂]⁺[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (R' = Me (8), Et (9), CH₂Ph (10)) and [Raai(CH₃)(CH₂Ph)⁺]₄[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (11)) are obtained by mixing methanol and 2-methoxy-ethanol mixture (2 : 1 v/v) of BiI₃ to methanol solution of [RaaiR'₂]⁺I⁻ or [RaaiR'R'']⁺I⁻ in 1 : 2 mole ratio at room temperature. It is filtered and washed with cold water and dried *in vacuo*. These compounds are recrystallised from methanol and 2-methoxy-ethanol (2 : 1 v/v) by slow evaporation in air. The composition of the compounds is supported by elemental analyses (C, H, N) and the structures are established by spectroscopic data. The single crystal X-ray diffraction measurements determine confirmed structure of the compounds (*vide infra*). Iodo-bismuthate(III) salts, **8-11**, are high conducting and show 4 : 1 conductivity in acetonitrile.

Spectral studies

The infrared frequencies of the compounds are assigned on comparing with free ligand data²¹. Moderately intense stretching at 1595–1600 and 1435–1445 cm⁻¹ is due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, respectively, for these compounds.

The compounds are soluble in acetonitrile and hence, the solution electronic spectra are recorded in solution at the wavelength range, 200–900 nm. There are three bands and out of them two are high intense (ϵ , 10⁴ mol⁻¹ dm³ cm⁻¹) bands at 350–360 and 370–380 nm. On comparing with free ligand spectra²¹, we may conclude that these bands are due to intramolecular charge transfer transitions. A weak band (ϵ , 10³ mol⁻¹ dm³ cm⁻¹) appears at 460–475 nm.

The ¹H NMR spectra of 1,3-dialkyl-2-(aryloxy)imidazolium iodide, [RaaiR'₂]⁺I⁻ (4-6) and [RaaiR'R'']⁺I⁻ (7) are taken in CDCl₃. The atom numbering pattern is shown in Scheme 1. The spectral data are set out in Table 2. The proton signals are assigned on the basis of spin-spin

interaction and effect of substitution. 1,3-Dialkyl-2-(aryloxy)imidazolium iodide show a single resonance for two R' : 1,3-Me₂ of 4 shows a sharp singlet at 4.25 ppm; 1,3-Et₂ of [RaaiEt₂]⁺I⁻ (5) exhibits 1-(CH₂)- and 3-(CH₂)- as quartet at av. 4.85 ppm and methyl (-Me) appears as triplet splitting pattern at av. 1.5 ppm. In 6, [Raai(CH₂Ph)₂]⁺I⁻ the significant observation is a strong singlet at 5.7–5.9 ppm that is assigned to -CH₂-(Ph) signal. Imidazole protons (4-, 5-H) appear as broad single resonance at 7.0–7.2 ppm. The broadening may be due to rapid proton exchange between two positions. The aryl protons (7-H to 11-H) are perturbed by 9-R substituent : 9-Me group shifts the proton signal to upfield side due to +I effect.

Molecular structure of [MeaaiMe₂]⁺₄[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (8b)

The crystal structure of [MeaaiMe₂]⁺₄[Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻ (8b) is shown in Fig. 1 and bond parameters are given in Table 3. The structure shows a one-dimensional chain constructed from [MeaaiMe₂]⁺ and [Bi₄I₁₆]⁴⁻. Aromatic rings of cation (imidazole and *p*-tolyl) interact through

R = H (a), Me (b), R' = R'' = -¹²CH₃ (1, 4, 8); -¹²CH₂¹³CH₃ (2, 5, 9), -¹²CH₂Ph (3, 6, 10); R' = Me, R'' = CH₂Ph (11)
Scheme 1. Syntheses of ligands RaaiR' (1-3), [RaaiR'R'']⁺I⁻ (4-7) and [RaaiR'₂]⁺₄[Bi₃I₁₆]⁴⁻ (8-10) and [Raai(Me)CH₂Ph]⁺₄[Bi₃I₁₆]⁴⁻ (11).

Table 2. ^1H NMR data of the complexes in $\text{DMSO}-d^6$

Complexes	δ , ppm (<i>J</i> , Hz)						
	4- H^a	5- H^a	7,11- H^b	8,10- H	9- Me^d	1-(3-)- Me	1-(3-)- CH_2
$[\text{HaaiMe}_2]_4^+[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ (8a)	7.56	7.56	8.03 (7.9)	7.50 ^c	–	4.42 ^d	–
$[\text{MeaaiMe}_2]_4^+[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ (8b)	7.58	7.58	7.95 (7.0)	7.43 ^b (9.0)	2.53	4.27 ^d	–
$[\text{HaaiEt}_2]_4^+[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ (9a)	7.55	7.55	7.99 (8.0)	7.49 ^c	–	1.63 ^e (7.0)	4.85 ^g (10.0)
$[\text{MeaaiEt}_2]_4^+[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ (9b)	7.60	7.60	7.89 (6.9)	7.33 ^b (9.0)	2.56	1.59 ^e (7.0)	4.88 ^g (10.0)
$[\text{Haai}(\text{CH}_2\text{Ph})_2]_4^+[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ (10a) ^f	7.54	7.54	7.93 (8.0)	7.55 ^c	–	–	5.69 ^d
$[[\text{Meaai}(\text{CH}_2\text{Ph})_2]_4^+[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ (10b) ^f	7.50	7.50	7.90 (8.0)	7.40 ^b (8.0)	2.50	–	5.89 ^d
$[\text{HaaiMe}(\text{CH}_2\text{Ph})]_4^+[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ (11a) ^f	7.52	7.52	7.87 (8.1)	7.58 ^c	–	4.35 ^d	5.77 ^d
$[\text{MeaaiMe}(\text{CH}_2\text{Ph})]_4^+[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ (11b) ^f	7.51	7.51	7.98 (8.0)	7.47 ^b (8.0)	2.54	4.77 ^d	6.05 ^d

^aBroad singlet; ^bdoublet; ^cmultiplet; ^dsinglet; ^e $\delta(-\text{N}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3)$; ^f $-\text{CH}_2\text{Ph}$ and δ of Ph protons lie 7.33–7.50 ppm, ^gquartet.

Fig. 1(b). The tetranuclear cluster anion, $[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ of **8b** formed by $\mu\text{-I}$ and $\mu\text{-I}$ bridgings.**Table 3.** Selected bond lengths and bond angles of $[\text{MeaaiMe}_2^+]_4[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ (**8b**)

Bond length (\AA)		Bond angle ($^\circ$)	
Bi(1)–I(8)	2.8899(6)	I(8)–Bi(1)–I(4)	95.240(19)
Bi(1)–I(4)	2.9301(6)	I(8)–Bi(1)–I(2)	91.07(2)
Bi(1)–I(2)	3.0575(7)	I(4)–Bi(1)–I(2)	91.495(17)
Bi(1)–I(1)	3.1004(6)	I(8)–Bi(1)–I(1)	89.34(2)
Bi(1)–I(3)	3.3301(7)	I(4)–Bi(1)–I(1)	93.523(16)
Bi(1)–I(3)	3.3529(6)	I(2)–Bi(1)–I(1)	174.906(16)
Bi(2)–I(9)	2.9091(7)	I(8)–Bi(1)–I(3)	94.677(17)
Bi(2)–I(6)	2.9110(7)	I(4)–Bi(1)–I(3)	170.002(17)
Bi(2)–I(7)	2.9257(6)	I(2)–Bi(1)–I(3)	87.053(15)
Bi(2)–I(1)	3.3340(7)	I(1)–Bi(1)–I(3)	87.853(15)
Bi(2)–I(3)	3.3400(7)	I(8)–Bi(1)–I(3)	173.612(18)
Bi(2)–I(2)	3.3797(7)	I(4)–Bi(1)–I(3)	88.289(16)
N(1)–N(2)	1.269(7)	I(2)–Bi(1)–I(3)	94.162(17)
N(5)–N(6)	1.127(10)	I(1)–Bi(1)–I(3)	85.124(16)
		I(3)–Bi(1)–I(3)	81.957(14)
		I(9)–Bi(2)–I(6)	96.14(2)
		I(9)–Bi(2)–I(7)	91.03(2)
		I(6)–Bi(2)–I(7)	98.191(18)
		I(9)–Bi(2)–I(1)	174.80(2)
		I(6)–Bi(2)–I(1)	88.577(17)
		I(7)–Bi(2)–I(1)	86.119(17)
		I(9)–Bi(2)–I(3)	94.26(2)

cross $\pi\text{---}\pi$ interaction to generate a 1-D chain (Fig. 2). Anion, exists as iodide bridge tetranuclear cluster; (Fig. 1(b)) via Bi(1)–I(1)–Bi(2) and Bi(1)–I(3)–Bi(2) bridges and cyclic dimerisation generates Bi_4 unit. In anion cluster $[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ Bi^{III} exists as BiI_6 octahedra and I binds in three different structural form – terminal iodine Bi(1)–I(4/8), 2.90–2.93 \AA , doubly bridged iodine Bi(1)– $\mu\text{-I}$ (1/2), 3.1 \AA and triply bridged iodine Bi(1)– $\mu\text{-I}$ (3), 3.33–3.35 \AA (symmetry – $-x, -y, -z$). The cluster is electro-

Fig. 2. π --- π interactions between *p*-tolyl and imidazole rings among organic (C = Cyan, N = Blue).

statically attracted to organic cation and are connected to four different $[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ through C-H---I hydrogen bonding interactions (Fig. 3). The iodobismuthate cluster is placed between organic layers and a 3D supramolecular structure is formed by both hydrogen bonding and π --- π interactions (Fig. 4). The thermal stability of the cluster is established by determining unit cell parameters at three different temperatures at 293, 303, and 313 K. The cell parameters remain more or less same. However, we can not do the experiment at higher temperature. The reversible dynamic structural change in the solid state of tetranuclear cubic cluster to 1D BiI_4 chains and 1D helical molecular chains are not observed in this case. The stability of cluster anion is remarkably depending on the templating effect of cations and in this example, the cross π --- π interaction (Fig. 2, Table 4) between imidazole of one cation and *p*-tolyl of adjacent cation $[\text{MeaiMe}_2]^+$ may be the reason to tolerate vibrational relaxation and debarring the cluster breakage. Each organic tetramer units are connected to four different $[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ through C-H---I hydrogen bonding interactions (Fig. 3) C(11)---H(11)---I(1) (H(11)---I(1), 3.010(2) Å; C(11)---I(1), 3.820(9) Å; $\angle\text{C(11)---H(11)---I(1)}$, 143°; symmetry - 1-x, 1-y, 1-z) and C(23)---H(23a)---I(9) (H(23a)---I(9), 3.040(3) Å; C(23)---I(9), 3.947(11) Å; $\angle\text{C(23)---H(23a)---I(9)}$, 158°; symmetry - 1-x, 1-y, -z). The 3D supramolecular structure is formed by both hydrogen bonding and π --- π interactions (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Each organic tetramer units are connected to four different $[\text{Bi}_4\text{I}_{16}]^{4-}$ through C-H---I hydrogen bonding interactions (C = Cyan, N = Blue, Bi = Orange, I = Yellow, H = Grey).

DFT and TD-DFT calculation

DFT calculations are currently used to establish the electronic structure, spectral transitions, and redox properties of different compounds. The calculated structure correlates well with the results of its X-ray analysis. The theoretical N=N, C=N, C=C and single bonds C-C, N-N, C-N, Bi-I are slightly longer (0.01–0.05 Å) than that of single crystal X-ray analysis data.

The DFT calculations have been done using optimized geometry of 8b. The surface plots of the MOs are given in Fig. 5. The composition of MOs shows that the occupied MOs are mainly composed of iodine (>90%) while unoccupied MOs (except LUMO) are made of MeaiMe_2^+ ion. The organic cation consists of azo, *p*-tolyl and imidazolium motifs; the LUMO+1 and LUMO+2 carry these three units by significant amount; LUMO+1 has 51% - azo, 23% - *p*-tolyl and 26% - imidazolium ion and the LUMO+2 - 54% - azo, 13% - *p*-tolyl and 33% -

Fig. 4. 3D supramolecular structure formed by both hydrogen bonding (black color) and π - π interactions (green color) (C = Cyan, N = Blue, Bi = Orange, I = Yellow-greenish, H = Grey).

Table 4. The π - π interactions of complex 8b

Cgi...Cgj	Centroid separation (Å)	Dihedral angle (°)	Perpendicular distance between cgi and cgj (Å)	Symmetry
Cg1...Cg2	3.747(5)	9.8(4)	3.414(4)	1-x, 2-y, 1-z
Cg1...Cg4	3.786(6)	3.4(5)	3.530(4)	1-x, 2-y, 1-z
Cg2...Cg1	3.747(5)	9.8(4)	3.494(3)	1-x, 2-y, 1-z
Cg2...Cg3	3.868(6)	8.8(5)	3.520(3)	1-x, 2-y, 1-z
Cg3...Cg2	3.870(6)	8.8(5)	3.468(4)	1-x, 2-y, 1-z
Cg4...Cg1	3.787(6)	3.4(5)	3.447(5)	1-x, 2-y, 1-z

Cg1 : N(3)-C(8)-N(4)-C(9)-C(10); Cg2 : C(1)-C(2)-C(3)-C(4)-C(5)-C(6); Cg3 : N(7)-C(20)-N(8)-C(21)-C(22); Cg4 : C(13)-C(14)-C(15)-C(16)-C(17)-C(18).

imidazolium ion while higher energy unoccupied MOs (LUMO+3, LUMO+4 etc.) are dominated by *p*-tolyl and imidazolium ion function.

The solution electronic spectra are explained referring to the composition of occupied and unoccupied MOs and their energies. The compounds exhibit intense transitions at 350–380 nm, 250–300 nm and weak band at 400–420 nm. The transitions may be assigned to $\pi(I) \rightarrow$

Fig. 5. Surface plots of HOMO-1, HOMO, LUMO and LUMO+1 of 8b.

$\pi^*(\text{I}/\text{azo}/p\text{-Tolyl}/\text{Imz})^{40,41}$. The band at 300–350 nm is referred to $n/\pi(\text{I}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{N}=\text{N})$ while the transitions 250–200 nm is assigned to $\pi(\text{I}) \rightarrow \pi^*(p\text{-Tolyl})/\pi^*(\text{Imz})$.

Conclusion

2-(Arylazo)imidazoles (RaaiH) are double alkylated to form 1,3-dialkyl-2-(arylazo)imidazolium salts (RaaiR'R''⁺I⁻). They have been reacted with BiI₃ to synthesise [RaaiR'R''⁺]₄[Bi₄I₆]⁴⁻. All these salts are characterized by spectroscopic data (IR, UV-Vis, ¹H NMR). The structural confirmation has been done by single crystal X-ray diffraction studies. Iodobismuthate cluster [Bi₄I₆]⁴⁻ is attracted electrostatically and placed in the cationic 1D frame and interacted by hydrogen bonds. The cluster is thermodynamically stable which may be due to templating effect of the cross π - π interaction between imidazole and *p*-tolyl units of organic cation. The DFT computation has been used to explain the electronic structure and the electronic spectra of the compounds.

Supplementary materials

Crystallographic data for the structure [MeaiMe₂⁺]₄[Bi₄I₆]⁴⁻ (8b) has been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC No. 847908. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from the Director, CCDC, 12, Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK (E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or www: <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

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